

Email templates to invite people to join your preprint journal club

Below, we have written four template emails you can tweak and send to your department to invite students, postdocs, and faculty to join a preprint journal club.

Template email #1 (long and informational): Invite your colleagues to join you

Dear students, postdocs, and faculty,

*I am ... **[Introduce yourself if you are not already known by everyone]**. I would like to start a preprint journal club in our department. I recently decided to contribute to PREREVIEW's **[optional: add link]** effort to promote the use and dissemination of preprints in academia and their review. For those of you who are not familiar with them, preprints are complete pieces of scientific work that have not yet undergone editorial peer review.*

The main benefits of posting preprints are that i) you, the author(s), can immediately share your work with the scientific community (but really with everyone, since preprints are open access, i.e., free!) without having to wait for the publisher's timeline, and ii) the community learn about your research early and can comment on the manuscript, potentially improving your work – since preprints are dynamic articles, you can incorporate the feedback and upload revisions to the preprint server of your choice.

Discussing preprints at a journal club will be beneficial to us as we will get to know the advancement in our field 6 months to a year earlier than we would if we waited for the publication. At the end of each journal club, we will compile our comments into a review and post it as a public document on PREREVIEW.org, a web platform that hosts preprint reviews and assigns them DOIs for free. In addition to this being useful to the authors and others who are interested in the science, I see posting reviews as an opportunity for early career researchers like myself to learn how to write a peer review.

[Here you can invite people to join the first meeting you have already scheduled] Our first meeting will be on ... at the Join us and let's learn together!

[...or you can ask for help organizing the journal club and brainstorm ideas on when, where, and how to do it to maximize attendance in your department, etc.]

If you want to help me organize the preprint journal club, please reply to this email. Ideally, I would like to meet for the journal club weekly or every other week, at a time and day of the week that best works for everybody who is interested.

Thank you,

[Your Name]

Template email #2: Short(er) and to the point

Dear students, postdocs, and faculty,

I am ... [Introduce yourself if you are not already known by everyone]. I would like to start a preprint journal club in our department. Preprints are complete pieces of scholarly work that have not yet undergone editorial peer review. At the end of each journal club, we will compile our comments into a review and post it as a public document on [PREreview.org](https://prereview.org), an online platform that hosts preprint reviews and assigns them DOIs for free.

[Here you can either invite people to join the first meeting you have already scheduled] Our first meeting will be on ... at the Join us and let's learn together! [...or you can ask for help organizing the journal club and brainstorm ideas on when, where, and how to do it to maximize attendance in your department, etc.]

If you want to help me organize the preprint club please reply to this email. Ideally, I would like to meet for the preprint club [INSERT FREQUENCY], at a time and day of the week that best works for everybody who is interested.

Thank you,

[Your Name]

Template email #3: Q&A format—good for generating initial interest, more informal

(This template was written by Dr. Emmy Tsang, Innovation Officer at [eLife](#))

Dear All,

I'm running a Preprint Journal Club. 30-second summary: if you have an hour to spare to discuss the latest science, help fellow researchers, make a difference to publishing, and eat [food], [\[put your name here/reply to this email\]](#)

What is a preprint? A manuscript that has yet to undergo journal-organized peer review.

What is a Journal Club? An occasion where we sit together to discuss a scientific paper—what we like and don't like. What is SPECIAL about a preprint journal club? We discuss a preprint instead of a published paper. Because the preprint is not yet published, our comments and suggestions might actually make a difference to the final published paper.

Cool... but how is that done? Via [PREreview.org](#), we will publish our feedback as a review for the preprint. This PREreview gets a DOI, will be public, and will also be sent to the authors of the preprint.

Why should I spend time and effort to give feedback to other researchers' manuscripts?

- 1. If you're a student: it's a really important part of your scientific career, to be able to understand and critique other people's research and results.*
- 2. Postdocs + students: reviewing papers is a huge part of a PI's job- this is an excellent opportunity to practice*
- 3. Everyone: publishing sucks. There's a lot of talk about how long and tedious the process is, but here's a chance to actually do something to change it. You're contributing to the exploration of alternative ways to get results out and advance science faster.*

*"But... I'm just a student, I don't know how to write reviews/make valid scientific comments..."
Well, I don't either. That's why this is a discussion—we can teach each other! There will be some materials to guide us through (also so that it doesn't go on forever!).*

I have tons of experiments. I don't have time. Free food, and I promise it will finish on time!

"OK, I'm sold. What do I do next?" Reply to this email, so I can keep you in the loop! My plan is [some specifics about the Journal Club. You can also ask for suggestions on the format, preprints, etc.]

"I have questions/suggestions..." Come talk to me! This is honestly an experiment- I would love to hear from you how to make it work :)

Best,

[Your Name]

Template email #4: send it to the preprint's corresponding author after you publish your review

Dear [corresponding author's name],

I am [insert your name and affiliation] and together with other researchers, I recently discussed your preprint ([insert title or DOI of preprint]) during our journal club meeting. I am a member of PREreview, a platform and a community that aims to support early-career researchers in presenting and reviewing preprints by providing resources to guide them through the process of peer review. Using these resources, we have compiled a review of your preprint, summarizing the feedback from the preprint club. The review is openly available on [PREreview.org](#) ([insert DOI or the link to your review]).

We hope the preprint review will be useful to you, and we welcome any comments you may have in response. If you would like to respond to the review, you can leave comments directly on the review by selecting the text and clicking on the commenting icon at the top of the page.

Kind regards,

[Your Name]